

Openness of performance-based funding for research and valorisation in Flanders since 2004

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In this paper I reflect on aspects of openness and discussions concerning possibilities for openness in the performance-based funding systems for research and valorisation that are in place for universities and higher education institutions in Flanders since 2004 (Luwel, 2021). Comparability, quantification and transparency across institutions are essential elements of a performance-based funding system that distributes subsidies across those institutions. Nonetheless, the need and wish to take into account diversity and impact resurfaces regularly. Within institutions many examples of valuation of activities and results beyond those that can be measured comparatively are apparent. In sum, the meaning of openness and taking into account diversity and impact differs depending on levels of governance and goal-orientation.

1. Introduction

The University Research Fund (BOF) provides the five Flemish universities with funds for basic research, and the Industrial Research Fund (IOF) provides the five associations of a university with one or more colleges of higher education with funds for applied research aimed at valorisation. Each university or association receives funds according to its share of the BOF key and IOF key, respectively. For the determination of these keys, the recent achievements on a number of parameters are important. For each parameter, the relative share of the university or association in the total of the relevant achievements of higher education institutions in Flanders is taken into account.

For a complete overview of the evolution of the distribution mechanisms of the BOF key and IOF key I refer to the review article by Mark Luwel (Luwel, 2021) and an earlier article by Raf Guns and myself (Engels & Guns, 2018). I here limit myself to the parameters that apply for the period 2024 to 2028 and the negotiations on openness, diversity and impact that some of these parameters have triggered and trigger in this era of open science.

2. Parameters in the Flemish performance-based funding models

The parameters in the BOF key 2024 are divided into three parts. The structural part A, which is based on performance in the past five-year period and which determines 50 percent of the BOF key. Part B, which includes peer-reviewed publications (15 percent) and citations of those publications (7.5 percent). And part C, which emphasizes training of young researchers (doctorates delivered, 9 percent), the relative citation impact of publications (10 percent), publications in international cooperation (3.75 percent), funding acquired from successive European framework programs for research and innovation (3.75 percent) and diversity of the population of researchers (1 percent).

The IOF key 2024 consists of six parameters. The first two parameters, 'doctorates defended' and the 'share of publications and citations', each determine the key by 5 percent and are calculated as in the BOF key, but at the level of each association. The parameter 'funding acquired from successive European framework programs' (20 percent) is also very similar to the parameter of the same name in the BOF key - the only difference being that the relevant funding acquired by the higher education colleges is also factored in. The three remaining parameters are specific to the IOF and together determine the lion's share of the IOF key (70

percent). The 'revenue from industry' parameter (30 percent) consists of the sum of revenue from contracts with companies, revenue from licenses and revenue from Phase 1 and Phase 2 clinical trials. The 'patents' parameter (20 percent) accounts for the number of published patent applications and the number of patents granted in Europe and the US. Finally, the 'spin-offs' parameter (20 percent) relates to the number of companies created with intellectual property or other knowledge of one of the institutions of the association with which an exclusive license was concluded within a year of its creation.

3. Openness of publication parameters

For each of the publication parameters, collaboration is encouraged in the sense that whole counting (Sivertsen, Rousseau & Zhang, 2019) is applied. For example, a publication to which two or more universities contribute is fully taken into account for each of the universities involved. The same then applies to the citations of those publications and their citation impact. Similarly, joint doctorates also count in full for both universities involved. This practice stimulates cooperation Flemish higher education institutions as well as international cooperation. This favourable treatment of cooperation is a key characteristic of the BOF-mechanism. However, whereas the share of publications in international collaboration has increased to over 70% of all peer-reviewed publications by Flemish universities, the relative intensity of collaboration (RIC, Fuchs & Rousseau, 2021) as calculated from the publications in the social sciences and humanities co-authored among Flemish universities has barely evolved since 2000 (e.g. the RIC between the universities of Ghent and Leuven hovers around 0,2).

In view of the open science agenda, however, the limitation of the publications counts to articles, proceedings papers and reviews indexed in Web of Science or peer reviewed journal articles, proceedings papers, book chapters, edited volumes and monographs approved for VABB-SHW (Verleysen, Ghesquière, & Engels, 2014) is sometimes voiced as a concern. Non-traditional outputs such as datasets and peer reviewed contributions in new journals or formats often do not fit the criteria of the BOF-regulation. Even though this does not need to have implications for the researchers involved, the fact that the performance-based funding system somehow limits the publication counts to more established publication channels that apply peer review, is sometimes cited as a hindrance in the evolution towards open science. At the same time, several in-depth analyses have pointed out that broadening up criteria in a consistent and reliable way (i.e. allowing for comparability, quantification and transparency) is hardly feasible. As a result, the one major change that stands out is the addition of the VABB-SHW itself, whereby the need to open up the publication count in view of the diversity of the publication cultures of the social sciences and humanities got recognized, albeit only insofar as peer review applied.

The limits to the possibilities and desirability of opening up publications counts have also been illustrated by questionable publishing practices. Screening for publications in possible questionable publication channels has been in place for several years (Eykens, Guns, Rahman & Engels, 2019) and proved important to counter media critiques of publishing practices. The many issues of how to define and identify questionable publishing notwithstanding, this also illustrates the need for a delimitation of publication counts for a performance-based funding system to maintain credibility towards societal actors such as media, politicians and businesses.

4. Openness of funding parameters

Funding parameters are in themselves a controversial component of performance-based funding systems. Funding streams may have widely different goals, that may or may not be in line with the goals of performance-based funding provided by the government. For example, performance-based research funding systems often aim at stimulating excellent research (Hicks,

2012), yet funding streams often have other aims too, such as tackling societal challenges. Moreover, the funding needs and possibilities to attract funding differ substantially across fields of science, disciplines and specialisms.

The aforementioned limitations help explain why, up until 2018, funding parameters were included in the IOF-key only. Only from 2019 onwards, the funding acquired from the European framework programs became a parameter in the BOF-key too. This decision was not taken lightly and was motivated by the desire to further stimulate excellence (e.g. funding from the European Research Council), talent development (e.g. funding through the Marie-Skłodowska Curie funding schemes), and internationalisation (e.g. participation in Horizon Europe cluster projects). Given the complexity of the framework programs and both small and substantial changes that occur during and in between the framework programs (e.g. from Horizon 2020 to Horizon Europe) differentiating further then at the umbrella of the overall programs seemed undesirable. Moreover, all income from the framework programmes is represented in the dashboard from the European Commission (Myklebust, 2024).

Possibilities for opening up have arguably come up more prominently in the IOF parameter 'funding from industry'. Although at first sight this may seem a straightforward incentive towards collaboration with industry, 'industry' is in itself not a precisely delineated part of the economy. Industry is part of the business sector, which also includes service companies, small and medium sized companies, and businesses that are majority owned by government. Industry does not, however, include other private sector actors such as non-profit organisations. Arguably, including those would create more room for income that represents activities that are more geared towards societal and mixed societal-economic impacts.

5. Openness of innovation parameters

Ultimately, funding provided to universities and colleges for higher education should translate into real world innovations. The long timelines that this often requires, make it impossible to rely on those measurements in view of performance-based funding distribution. Moreover, once research leaves the proverbial lab, many factors beyond the realm of the university will determine the real world impact of those innovations. Such reflections have often been raised regarding the IOF parameters for patents and spin-offs, including the possibility to make them more open and/or to make them reflect impact more accurately. For example the possibility to measure also the size or the growth of spin-offs resonates well with the wish for fast growing companies, including unicorns. However, different ways of measuring the size of (non-listed) companies are hard to compare, and in any case a few years after the start of a spin-off company its' developments do not depend that much on the characteristics of the university's innovative activity anymore. Similarly, although a patent application and even a granted patent in itself do not yet represent real-world innovation, including patents as indicators of innovation allows for comparable, quantitative and transparent measurement of results that are intended towards innovation. From the government's point of view, including such a parameter in a scheme that aims at applied research and valorisation makes sense, even though such an indicator represents only a small part of the multivariate role of universities in the current era of open innovation ecosystems (Bogers & Steinbuch, 2023).

6. Conclusion

The Flemish universities are strong performers in terms of research and innovation. The fact that the BOF and IOF subsidies come as ringfenced funding emphasizes government expectations in these areas. The performance-based funding systems by which the BOF and IOF subsidies are distributed, however, are a balancing act that aim to reconcile ambitions relating to competitiveness, diversity, innovation ecosystems, and openness. Few studies analyse performance-based funding systems in depth and those that do mainly focus on

publications (e.g. Ossenblok, Engels & Sivertsen, 2012), which is only one aspect. Luwel (2021) reports having identified no comparative studies on inclusion of patents, European or international funding, or funding from the business sector in performance-based funding mechanisms. We encourage the STI community to engage in such studies, using a diversity of methods.

Open science practices

Several of the data that contribute to the annual calculation of the BOF- and the IOF-key are available online through <https://www.vlaamsindicatorenboek.be/>. The data of the Flemish Academic Bibliography for the Social Sciences and Humanities (VABB-SHW) is available as an open dataset. The most recent instalment is edition 13, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10534442>.

Competing interests

As initiator of the ECOOM-Antwerp branch in 2007, coordinator of the VABB-SHW in the period 2008-2015, supervisor of the ECOOM-Antwerp branch since 2014, and staff member of the research, innovation and valorisation services at University of Antwerp, I have been closely involved in the developments and negotiations regarding performance-based funding in Flanders since 2009.

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